
Postural Hand Synergies during Environmental Constraint Exploitation

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Humans are able to intuitively exploit the shape of an object and environmental constraints
4 to achieve stable grasps and perform dexterous manipulations. In doing that, a vast range
5 of kinematic strategies can be observed. However, in this work we formulate the hypothesis
6 that such ability can be described in terms of a synergistic behavior in the generation of hand
7 postures, i.e. using a reduced set of commonly used kinematic patterns. This is in analogy with
8 previous studies showing the presence of such behavior in different tasks, such as grasping.
9 We investigated this hypothesis in experiments performed by six subjects, who were asked
10 to grasp objects from a flat surface. We quantitatively characterized hand posture behaviour
11 from a kinematic perspective, i.e. the hand joint angles, in both pre-shaping and during the
12 interaction with the environment. To determine the role of tactile feedback, we repeated the same
13 experiments but with subjects wearing a rigid shell on the fingertips to reduce cutaneous afferent
14 inputs. Results show the persistence of at least two postural synergies in all the considered
15 experimental conditions and phases. Tactile impairment does not alter significantly the first two
16 synergies, and contact with the environment generates a change only for higher order Principal
17 Components. A good match also arises between the first synergy found in our analysis and
18 the first synergy of grasping as quantified by previous work. The present study is motivated
19 by the interest of learning from the human example, extracting lessons that can be applied in
20 robot design and control. Thus, we conclude with a discussion on implications for robotics of our
21 findings.

22 **Keywords:** Postural Synergies, Human Hand Motor Control, Environment Constraint Exploitation, Tactile Perception, Grasping

1 INTRODUCTION

23 The human hand is a remarkably complex system, with many joints, ligaments, muscles, and sensory
24 receptors contributing to its wide dexterity. The control of such an abundance or redundancy is classically
25 referred to as Bernstein's problem (Bernstein, 1967). Several neuroscientific findings (Mussa-Ivaldi,

26 1999; Sauter et al., 2001; Latash, 2008; Overduin et al., 2014; Stratmann et al., 2016) suggest that the
27 human nervous system is able to cope with such complexity leveraging on a control space of reduced
28 dimensionality. Under this regard, synergies were defined as principal patterns of actuation. Through them,
29 the human Central Nervous System, also leveraging upon peripheral constraints, can generate movements
30 by combining pre-organized patterns, i.e. by simultaneously activating different degrees of freedom, instead
31 of acting separately on each joint or muscle. These patterns are implemented at various level of the motor
32 control architecture, i.e. either they are represented by cortical mechanisms, hard-coded in low level neural
33 circuits, or generated by the mechanical organization of human musculoskeletal system (Tresch et al.,
34 1999; Santello et al., 2013; Leo et al., 2016). The synergy concept has been investigated in different tasks.
35 Examples regarding hand control are grasping imagined objects (Santello et al., 1998), reach-to-grasp
36 (Mason et al., 2001), precision grip (Grinyagin et al., 2005).

37 Another key aspect in the generation of meaningful motor actions was recognized in the interplay between
38 synergistic components and the external environment (Feldman et al., 2015). Indeed, from a sensory point
39 of view, it plays a crucial role to build up our knowledge of the world. Under this regard, a well-known
40 characterization of hand movements during the exploration of the environment is represented by the
41 Exploratory Procedures identified by Lederman and Klatzky (Lederman and Klatzky, 1990). Exploratory
42 Procedures are stereotyped hand motions characteristic of human haptic exploration of the environment.
43 By applying these procedures, subjects try to maximize the amount of haptic information acquired from
44 external objects. Thakur et al. (Thakur et al., 2008) analyzed Exploratory Procedures through Principal
45 Component Analysis, identifying a reduced set of postural synergies generating the observed behavior.

46 Focusing instead on the use of constraints for effective motor task accomplishment, Environmental
47 Constraint Exploitation (ECE) primitives are defined in (Eppner et al., 2015). We will refer in the following
48 to ECE strategies as actions which aim to manipulate or grasp an object, and involve the use of a constraint
49 as central element of the strategy. Fig. 1 shows some examples reproducing experimentally observed
50 behaviors, where a subject exploits a flat surface. In (Puhlmann et al., 2016) a taxonomy of ECE primitives
51 is proposed. In (Eppner et al., 2015), authors also show that impairing the use of the environment during
52 grasping and manipulation sensibly decreases subjects performance, suggesting the central role of these
53 strategies in humans. This way of manipulating and grasping is very different from the classical strategies
54 used in robotics, where the contact with the environment is avoided as much as possible (Bonilla et al.,
55 2014). Thus, it is authors opinion that a deeper understanding of ECE can directly affect the performance
56 of robotic manipulators.

57 In this work we investigate the presence of a synergistic behavior underlying the generation of hand
58 postures during ECE, execution and planning. We also investigate the effect that cutaneous impairment
59 might have on such synergies. We were motivated in doing this by the many studies in literature highlighting
60 the central role of tactile information in grasping (Johansson and Westling, 1984; Westling and Johansson,
61 1987; Nowak et al., 2004).

62 We performed experiments with six participants, who were asked to grasp a set of objects from a
63 flat surface. We selected this task since it represents a good trade-off between analytic complexity and
64 richness of kinematic behavior induced by ECE, as accounted e.g. by Fig. 1 and in (Eppner et al., 2015).
65 Two experimental conditions were considered: with and without cutaneous impairment. In the first case,
66 participants were requested to wear rigid shells at their fingertips. Results were processed through Principal
67 Component Analysis, as it is common in literature (Santello et al., 2013), in order to check the existence of
68 a set of Principal Components describing the recorded data. We performed the analysis during the actual

Figure 1. Photo sequences of some examples of experimental constraint exploitation (one for each row). In the first two rows, the subject uses the surface to guide the fingertips position and robustly grasp the object (pinch grasp in the first row, power grasp in the second). In the third row the subject uses the surface to re-orientate the object. In rows four and five, two thin objects are grasped by flipping them using the surface as pivot. In the last row, the subject shifts the object by sliding it through the surface to the edge of the table, where it can be efficiently grasped. From these few examples, we can observe a large variety of strategies and related hand postures.

69 contact with the environment and on pre-shaping postures, i.e., during the approaching movement that
70 precedes the hand-object-table interaction.

71 A marked synergistic behavior results in all the considered experiments. Both the interaction with the
72 external environment and the cutaneous impairment appear to modify only the higher order Principal
73 Components. Furthermore the first synergy exhibits a good resemblance with the one observed in grasping
74 of imagined objects (reported in (Santello et al., 1998)).

75 In recent years, the idea of hand synergies (with special focus on grasping) has been successfully applied
76 in robotics for a simplified yet effective design, sensing, and control of artificial systems. For a detailed
77 review, we refer the interested reader to (Santello et al., 2016; Alessandro et al., 2013). In accordance
78 with this previous successful experience of mutual inspiration between neuroscience and robotics, we
79 believe that the here proposed results can inform the design and control of artificial hands able to take full
80 advantage of the Exploitation of Environmental Constraints. We discuss these aspects in the final part of
81 the work.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

82 2.1 Participants

83 We tested six able-bodied volunteers (three females, three males; age range: 23–27 years, mean 25.17
84 years). All subjects were tested on their dominant hand (right hand; self-reported hand dominance). All
85 participants were naive to the experimental purpose of the study and had no history of neuromuscular
86 disorders. Before data collection, subjects signed an informed consent to participate in the experiment.
87 The experimental protocols were approved by the Institutional Review Board of University of Pisa, in
88 accordance to the declaration of Helsinki.

89 2.2 Apparatus

90 For the present investigation we employed a multimodal acquisition setup (see Fig. 2), composed of

- 91 • Phase Space Motion Capture System; we record kinematic data using a commercial system for 3D
92 motion tracking with active LED markers, the Phase Space¹. Ten stereo-cameras working at 480Hz
93 tracked 3D positions of 24 markers fastened to hand and phalanges as shown in Fig. 2a. The LED
94 frequency is in the visible red.
- 95 • A fingertip shell (Fig. 2b) ; we use the shell of ThimbleSense sensor (Battaglia et al., 2016). Subjects
96 wore Thimblesenses in all fingertips during the tactile impairment experiments, as in Fig. 2b. Each
97 shell is connected to the correspondent fingertip as in classical thimbles. Please refer to (Battaglia et al.,
98 2016) for a more extensive description of the impairment effects of the shells. Also force information is
99 acquired, to be used in future works. Subjects wore Thimblesenses on all fingertips, during the tactile
100 impairment experiments.
- 101 • A set of 21 objects (Fig. 2d); this is composed of 2 euro coin, button badge, key, credit card, CD,
102 comb hair color, salt shaker, tape, chessman (queen), knob, matchbox, screw, match, cigarette, rubber
103 band, marker, screw driver, shashlik, glasses, coffee mug, plat.
- 104 • Sensorized platform (600 × 400 mm), which includes the force-torque sensor ATI mini45E mounted as
105 in Fig. 2c. It allows the sensing of interaction forces/torques with the table where objects were placed.
- 106 • Two cameras (Logitech hd 1080p) to record from two viewpoints the experiments, as in Fig. 3f. The
107 recordings were used to visually check the effectiveness of the segmentation. We use blue filters to
108 improve the quality of the recording, which was reduced by the poor light conditions and the red light
109 emittance due to the motion capture system.

110 In contrast with previous work on grasping real objects (e.g. (Mason et al., 2001)), we chose objects
111 that are difficult to grasp and therefore necessitate exploitation of the flat surface constraint. A similar
112 set of objects was used in (Eppner et al., 2015) in an analogous table-top scenario, demonstrating the
113 effectiveness of eliciting a rich set of ECE strategies.

114 The acquisition is implemented through a custom application developed in C++ employing:

- 115 • Boost libraries (Schäling, 2011) to perform the synchronization between Phase Space data and
116 force/torque sensors;
- 117 • Phase Space OWL library to get the optical tracking system data
- 118 • A custom library providing an interface to acquire the force/torque sensor data (Serio et al., 2014).

¹ <http://www.phasespace.com/>, website visited on April 2017

(2a) LED distribution

(2b) ThimbleSense.

(2c) Sensorized surface

(2d) Set of objects used in the experiment.

Figure 2. Experimental apparatus. Kinematic measures are kept through an active marker motion capture system. Impaired condition is imposed through ThimbleSenses' rigid shells. Force and torque data were acquired from the sensorized table.

119 The acquisition system allows to organize and synchronize data with respect to an absolute clock with
120 period 0.025s.

121 2.3 Experiments

122 The experiments were designed with the aim of identifying kineto-static primitives used by humans in
123 grasping and manipulation tasks involving ECE. The subject was asked to comfortably seat in front of the
124 table, as in Fig. 3e. The subject was instructed to pose her/his hand in the initial hand position location,
125 positioned at the right side of the sensorized surface as in Fig. 3f. The distance between the subject's hand

126 starting position and the site where the object was placed was 60cm. For each trial, subjects were asked
 127 to reach the object posed in the center of the sensorized surface. Once the hand had reached the object,
 128 subjects were asked to grasp, lift (~ 20 cm height), hold (~ 1 s), put it back on the table, and place the
 129 hand back to its starting position. The experimenter gave the starting signal to subjects. In the instructions,
 130 the experimenter emphasized that the whole movement should be performed in a natural fashion, i.e. the
 131 object should be grasped as if the subject was about to use it, in accordance with (Santello et al., 1998).
 132 Two trials were performed for any of the 21 objects grasped. The object order was randomized for every
 133 subject. The sequence of trials was repeated two times, with and without tactile impairment, for a total
 134 of 84 trials per subject. Each subject performed the whole experiment in a single day. The experiments
 135 with tactile impairment were performed in the morning, the experiments without tactile impairment in the
 136 afternoon, in agreement with previous experiments (Battaglia et al., 2016). Each subject performed the
 137 experiment in an independent day w.r.t the other ones.

Figure 3. Experimental setup. The subjects sat comfortably in front of the table. In the starting position, subject's hand was located over the drawing on right side of the sensorized surface. In addition to the ten cameras used for the motion capture, two cameras are included in the setup to record the scene.

138 2.4 Data Pre-Processing and Analysis

139 Data processing is organized in two phases. First, data is pre-processed to reduce the noise and to
 140 evaluate joint angles and contact points. Second, we perform statistical analyses to identify the presence
 141 of a synergistic behavior in ECE. We perform the analyses in pre-shaping, and during the whole contact
 142 with the environment. To quantify the role of tactile impairment, we consider separately the impaired and
 143 unimpaired cases. The analysis was performed considering the whole group of participants. In section 3.4
 144 we report the CI for the dot products between the synergies' vectors.

145 2.4.1 Data Processing

146 Raw data collected from the experimental setup were force and torque from the six axes F/T sensor
 147 ATImini45 and 24 LED positions from the motion capture system, both with and without tactile impairment.

148 2.4.1.1 Kinematic Model of the Human Hand

149 An accurate description of the human hand is challenging due to the high number of bones and joints
 150 composing the human hand. As a trade-off between accuracy and complexity, in this work we considered
 151 a 20 DoF kinematic model of the human hand (Fig. 4g). Each long finger is described by a set of four

Figure 4. Kinematic model of the human hand considered in this work. The model has 20 DoFs, which include the 15 DoFs of the hand model used in (Santello et al., 1998). The left panel graphically describes the kinematics, while the right one specifies the Denavit-Hartenberg parametrization of thumb and the long fingers. We denoted with j the joint index, starting from the proximal joint to the distal, while q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 are the joint angles, and a_2, a_3, a_4 are the phalanx lengths.

152 angles: two DoFs for flexion-extension and abduction-adduction in metacarpophalangeal joints, one DoF
 153 for flexion-extension in proximal and distal intra-phalangeal joints. The thumb is described with four
 154 angles: two DoFs for the trapeziometacarpal, one DoF for the metacarpo-phalangeal, and one DoF for the
 155 interphalangeal. For the sake of space, we do not report here the mathematical form of the kinematics²,
 156 which can be easily derived from the Denavit-Hartenberg parametrization in Fig. 4h (see e.g. (Murray
 157 et al., 1994)). In the Appendix, we report the direct kinematics derivation for the led positioned on a long
 158 finger nail. A key characteristic of the model is that it shares the 15 DoFs of the model used in (Santello
 159 et al., 1998), allowing an easy comparison with the classical postural synergies of grasp, as done e.g. in
 160 (Gabiccini et al., 2013).

161 **2.4.1.2 Model Calibration**

162 To reconstruct realistic values of the joint angles from marker data, the kinematic model employed should
 163 reproduce as closely as possible the actual kinematics of the subject being recorded. To achieve this goal,
 164 we implement an identification procedure that follows what was done in (Gabiccini et al., 2013). The
 165 dataset is acquired by asking the subject to perform the Kapandji test (Kapandji, 1985), i.e. touching the
 166 four long fingers with the tip of the thumb. The test is repeated two times.

167 The parameters to be identified are: $a_B \in \mathbb{R}^{30}$ collecting the length of each phalanx and the three space
 168 positions of the abduction joints (TR/TA, IM/IA, MM/MA, RM/RA e LM/LA in Fig. 4g) w.r.t. the local

² Note that here we use the term kinematics as it is commonly done in robotics and biomechanics, to refer to the mapping of Lagrangian variables to a different point of the structure. In this context, the evolution in time is referred to as differential kinematics.

169 frame, and $a_G \in \mathbb{R}^{45}$ collecting the location of each marker placed on the phalanxes w.r.t. the joint to
 170 which the LED is connected.

171 Their values are evaluated as ones minimizing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between measured
 172 marked positions y_k and the estimated ones from the hand kinematics $f(x_k; a_G, a_B)$, in a set of reference
 173 time stamps \mathbb{K}_{id}

$$\begin{aligned} \arg \min_{x, a_G, a_B} & \sqrt{\sum_{k \in \mathbb{K}_{id}} (y_k - f(x_k; a_G, a_B))^T (y_k - f(x_k; a_G, a_B))} \\ \text{s.t. } & x_k > 0 \quad \forall k, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

174 where $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^{20}$ is the vector collecting the estimation of joint angles at the k -th time step, $x_k > 0$ is to
 175 be considered element-wise, x is the vector collecting all the joint estimations in the considered time steps.
 176 We selected \mathbb{K}_{id} as 60 equidistant frames. The constraint $x_k > 0$ accounts for biomechanical joint limits,
 177 in order to achieve a more robust estimation.

178 The optimization problem is solved through the MatLab function *fmincon*. The initial guess for the
 179 parameters a_G and a_B are evaluated through direct measurements, done with a caliper on each subject's
 180 hand before the experiment, while the initial value of x is the null vector. Since we do not have direct
 181 access to the real joint angles, the quality of the calibration is evaluated as the RMSE between the measured
 182 led positions, and the ones resulting from the identification, as e.g. in (Gabiccini et al., 2013). The average
 183 error across trials and subjects is 2.2mm for the unimpaired case and 3.1mm for the impaired case.

184 **2.4.1.3 Joint Angles Estimation**

185 Articulated hand postures typically produce marker occlusion to cameras. We use here Piecewise Cubic
 186 Hermite Interpolating Polynomials (De Boor et al., 1978) to interpolate missing values. To estimate the
 187 hand postures from marker position we propose a Constrained Extended Kalman Filter (Sircoulomb et al.,
 188 2008). Kalman filtering was already employed for a similar scope in (Fu and Santello, 2010). We rely on the
 189 identified hand model, representing joint evolution as a random walk. In each time step the filter estimates
 190 the hand posture from the measure of the marker position in space and previous state estimation. Joint
 191 limits are considered as constraints. To increase the robustness against marker losses (we had an average of
 192 2.47 marker loss per frame, and a maximum number of consecutive marker loss of ~ 15), we multiply at
 193 each step the Kalman Filter observation noise covariance matrix by the number of consecutive missing
 194 measures. The filter is initialized with the open hand posture, and a null state covariance matrix. The
 195 observation noise covariance matrix is $0.001 I_{20 \times 20}$ and the state noise covariance matrix is $0.0005 I_{24 \times 24}$.
 196 Both the matrices are heuristically tuned. The quality of the reconstruction is evaluated as the RMSE
 197 between measured and estimated LED positions. The mean values is 2.9mm for the unimpaired case and
 198 3.2mm for the impaired case.

199 **2.4.1.4 Force Data**

200 The force/torque data from ATI Mini45 (i.e. sensorised surface) are filtered through a moving average
 201 filter based on Savitzky-Golay method (Schafer, 2011). The window width is heuristically tuned as the
 202 1.5% of total data length. We then use the knowledge of surface form, to evaluate the centroid of contact of
 203 Force/Torque data³.

³ The contact points are computed through tactile toolbox, as in (Serio et al., 2014). A portable version of this tool as well as raw data of our experiments will be released through handcorpus.

204 2.4.2 Analysis

205 We segment pre-processed data into three main phases, also described in Fig. 5: i) pre-shaping, where the
206 object is reached and the hand posture is shaped in order to purposefully interact with the environment, ii)
207 contact, in which the constraint is exploited in order to manipulate and grasp the object, and iii) post-contact,
208 when the object is grasped and lifted from the table.

209 By considering non-adhesive interactions with the environment, we can assume any change occurring to
210 the force orthogonal to the surface as due to an interaction. We thus segmented the actions searching for a
211 change in the corresponding force measured by the sensorized surface (see Sec. 2.2). The cut off from the
212 first and the second phase is identified by the first contact with the table, when the force starts to increase.
213 To accurately detect this point we consider both to the signal and to its derivative. The cut off identifying
214 the end of the contact phase is taken as the first time in which the contact force returns to zero.

215 The aim of the analysis is to identify a subspace of reduced dimensionality embedding the hand postures,
216 to test the hypothesis of presence of a synergistic behavior in Environmental Constraint Exploitation.
217 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a valuable tool to achieve this goal (Santello et al., 1998; Mason
218 et al., 2001; Thakur et al., 2008; Santello et al., 2013). Given a set of data, described by a correlation matrix
219 C and a mean m , PCA derives an orthonormal base of the data space, whose first element S_1 indicates the
220 direction where data present the greatest variability. In turn, each successive component S_i has the highest
221 variability under orthogonality constraint. The i -th element of the base is referred as Principal Component
222 of the dataset. The normalized percentage of the data variability projected on each Principal Component is
223 called explained variance of the component.

224 We evaluate PCA as the singular value decomposition of the data correlation matrix C , i.e. by finding
225 an orthonormal matrix Σ , which brings C in Jordan form through the similitude transformation $\Sigma^T C \Sigma$.
226 In that case the Principal Components are the column of the matrix $\Sigma = [S_1, \dots, S_n]$, and the explained
227 variances are the corresponding eigenvalues. For further details on PCA we refer the interested reader to
228 (Jolliffe, 2002).

229 If PCA is used to analyze hand postures in joint space, explained variances can be used to understand if
230 the hand moves on a reduced set of the configurations by looking if there are few principal directions that
231 explain the major part of the data. If this is the case we refer to such principal directions as synergies.

232 It is worth noticing that the use of the same calibrated kinematic model for every subject enables a
233 coherent description of the hand configuration space as \mathbb{R}^{20} for all the experimental conditions. We
234 consider cosine of the angle between synergy's directions as the metric to compare results of the different
235 analyses. We evaluate it as the absolute value of the normalized dot product between the synergy vectors.

236 We also compare synergies resulting from our analysis with those employed for the execution of grasping,
237 as shown in (Santello et al., 1998). The kinematic model in (Santello et al., 1998) takes into account a
238 subset of the joints considered in this work (see Sec. 2.4.1.1). Thus the configuration space of grasping
239 synergies is a sub-set of dimension 15 of the hand configuration space considered in this work. To compare
240 vectors, we projected full hand configurations in the corresponding sub-space. This is equivalent to simply
241 neglect the values corresponding to joints ID, MD, RD and LD in Fig. 4g.

242 Since our main focus is to extract lessons that can inform the robotic design (as discussed in Sec. 4.2), a
243 complete study of inference is beyond the scope of the present work. However we considered t-student
244 method to infer the general validity of some of our results. Please refer to (Hogg and Craig, 1995) for an
245 exhaustive introduction.

Figure 5. Photo-sequences of experimental constraint exploitation. According to our contact based classification, (a) presents the *pre-shaping* phase, (b) shows the *during contact* phase, and (c) the *post-contact* phase.

246 2.4.2.1 Pre-shaping analysis

247 The pre-shaping analysis is done with the purpose of identifying kinematic regularities in the generation
 248 of hand postures for the ECE exploitation. In (Santello et al., 1998) PCA is performed for constant postures
 249 acquired in grasping. There authors took out effects due to interaction with the objects, by asking subjects
 250 to grasp imagined ones. In this analysis we aim to achieve the same goal by performing PCA on a dataset
 251 composed of the last poses before the contact with the environment in each trial, i.e. the last pose in pre-
 252 shaping phases when a purposeful interaction with the environment is planned. Unimpaired and impaired
 253 cases are separately analyzed. Both datasets are composed of 252 poses (six subjects, 21 objects, two trials)

254 2.4.2.2 Contact analysis

255 In order to evaluate if there are some kinematic regularities in the strategies employed by the subjects
 256 during actual exploitation of the surface (see e.g. Fig. 1), we perform PCA on data collected during the
 257 contact phase. We perform the analysis separately in the impaired and unimpaired case. To characterize
 258 the effect of cutaneous impairment we also evaluated the mean amount of time in which subjects stay in
 259 contact with the table, mean time for task accomplishment, and the mean norm of interaction forces, by
 260 averaging the correspondent values for every subject and every object.

261 The datasets for both impaired and unimpaired conditions are composed of a variable number of poses
 262 depending on the strategy execution time. Each ECE generates an amount of postures equal to 40 times the
 263 execution time (see acquisition rate in Sec. 2.2). All 21 objects, two trials and six subjects were considered.

264 2.4.2.3 Differences between Pre and During contact

265 We investigate the persistence of the same basic ingredients of hand posture before and during the contact
 266 with the environment for both bare fingers and cutaneous impairment conditions. The dot product of
 267 synergies evaluated in previous sections was computed in order to quantify their similarities.

Figure 6. Explained variance resulting from PCA analysis of postures in pre-shaping and during contact, in tactile impaired and unimpaired case. A marked predominance of the first Principal Component is present in all the cases, showing a synergistic behavior.

3 RESULTS

268 3.1 Pre-shaping analysis

269 Fig. 6 shows the explained variance associated to the PCs on the poses during the pre-shaping phase.
 270 For the unimpaired case, the first Principal Component explains about 54% of the variance, while the first
 271 three pre-shaping synergies explain more than 72%. Fig. 7 shows the graphical representation of the first
 272 three resulting postural synergies. The same analysis in the impaired case shows that the first synergy
 273 explains about 42% of the variance, while three Principal Components explain more than 68% of the
 274 variance. Thus, for our dataset, the variance explained by the first main synergies is lower in the impaired
 275 condition. In Fig. 7 we present the graphical representations of the movements corresponding to the first
 276 three synergies of pre-shaping without tactile impairment. Tab. 1 presents the numerical values of the first
 277 ECE synergy of pre-shaping with and without impairment, in comparison with the first synergy of grasp
 278 (Santello et al., 1998). Fig. 8 presents the movement corresponding to the second synergy of pre-shaping
 279 with tactile impairment.

Figure 7. Graphical representation of the movements w.r.t. the mean hand posture, associated to the first three synergies during pre-shaping in unimpaired condition. Each column presents a different stage of the synergistic movement, obtained by summing the hand mean configuration m , to the synergy vector S_i of the i -th synergy.

280 In all the considered cases, the first synergy describes a opening-closing behavior of the whole hand,
 281 while the second synergy corresponds to a closure of the distal joints mostly of index and medial fingers,
 282 and a closing of the thumb. The third synergy is similar to the second, but concerning the little and ring
 283 fingers.

284 Fig. 9(a) shows the scalar product between the first grasp synergy in (Santello et al., 1998) and the
 285 ones found in this work for both sensory conditions. What is noticeable is that there is a high level
 286 of consistency between the main synergy of grasping and pre-shaping of human hand in impaired and
 287 unimpaired condition (≥ 0.9). The similarity is reduced for the second synergy, as shown in the same Fig.
 288 (b), and so on for the other orders. Fig. 9 reports also a high correlation between pre-shaping synergies with
 289 and without tactile impairment. The presence of impairment does not alter the first two synergies during
 290 the pre-shaping phase. However the similarity strongly drops when the synergy order increases further,
 291 reaching 0.36 for the third and 0.003 for the forth.

292 3.2 Contact analysis

293 In the unimpaired condition, the first Principal Component explains about the 49% of the variance, and
 294 the first three synergies more than 73%. The same analysis in the impaired case returns a first synergy

Figure 8. Graphical representation of the movements associated to the second ECE synergy. Pre-shaping impaired, contact unimpaired and contact impaired conditions are considered. The mean posture is referred as m , the second synergy as S_2 . We do not report here the first synergies, since they do not present visible discrepancies from each others. The present figure shows also a good coherence in the behavior described by the second synergy, among the considered conditions.

Figure 9. Dot products between first and second grasp synergies and first and second ECE synergies evaluated during pre-shaping, with and without tactile impairment. The gray scale graphically codes the product value: black is 1, i.e. very similar, white is 0, i.e. very different. A high correlation between the first grasping and ECE synergies is evidenced. The ECE synergies with and without impairment present high similarity, which however drops for higher order synergies.

295 explaining about the 39% of the variance, and the three Principal Components explaining more than 65%
 296 of the variance. Also in this case, for our dataset the percentage of variance explained in the impaired
 297 condition is lower. Tab. 1 presents the numerical values of first ECE synergy during the contact with
 298 the environment, with and without impairment, in comparison with the first synergy of grasp (Santello
 299 et al., 1998). Fig. 8 presents the movement corresponding to the second synergy with and without tactile
 300 impairment.

Figure 10. Dot products between the ECE synergies in pre-shaping and in contact with the environment, in the bare finger case. The gray scale graphically codes the product value: black is 1, i.e. very similar, white is 0, i.e. very different. A tendency to maintain the first main components before and after the contact results clearly from this analysis. The results for the impaired case are analogous.

301 The analysis also demonstrates that subjects with tactile impairment are in contact with the table for an
 302 average time of 4.2 ± 3.1 s, while for the unimpaired case the average time is 2.4 ± 2.4 s. The complete
 303 task is performed in 13.9 ± 2.7 s for the tactile impairment case, while it is performed in 11.5 ± 2.0 s in
 304 the other case. Finally, the contact force is different for the experiments considered. Mean value of norm of
 305 contact forces for the tactile impairment case is 23.2 ± 8.6 N, while mean value is 12.3 ± 5.7 N in the
 306 other case.

307 3.3 Differences between Pre and During contact

308 The result shows that the first Principal Components in unimpaired and impaired conditions are very
 309 similar w.r.t. the corresponding ones of the pre-shaping analysis. The similarity tends to decrease with the
 310 increase of synergy order (correlation ≥ 0.75 till 9th synergy). Dot products are graphically reported in Fig.
 311 10 for the unimpaired case. Thus ECs induce only changes for the high order synergies, leaving unaltered
 312 the main ones, regardless of availability of tactile input. Note that the first synergy is still equivalent to the
 313 one in (Santello et al., 1998).

314 3.4 Inference and Statistical Relevance

315 In the previous sections we presented results from 6 subjects. Despite such a moderate number of
 316 participants, findings and analyses are in line with the existing literature in the field, see e.g. Santello
 317 et al. (1998); Mason et al. (2001); Naceri et al. (2016). To generalize, we here report additional statistical
 318 analyses that provide t-Student based confidence intervals (CI) with 95% probability. CI refers to dot
 319 products performed on the PCs extracted for the different conditions, and the ones obtained in grasping.

320 CI for the dot product between the first synergy for impaired and unimpaired conditions is $[0.81, 0.96]$; CI
 321 for the dot product between the first grasping synergy and the unimpaired first ECE synergy is $[0.88, 0.94]$;
 322 CI for the dot product between the first grasping synergy and the impaired first ECE synergy is $[0.79, 0.9]$.

323 Regarding the contact analysis of Sec. 3.3, the dot product between the first Principal Component before
324 and during contact results in a CI of $[0.97, 0.99]$ (unimpaired case).

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

325 4.1 Implications for motor control

326 The explained variance reported in Fig. 6 suggests the presence of an underlying synergistic behavior
327 in the purposeful exploitation of environmental constraints. Indeed, the dimensionality of the space
328 required to approximate hand posture is considerably smaller than the number of degrees of freedom. In
329 particular, the first Principal Component shows a marked predominance, with a maximum total variance
330 explained of 54% in the unimpaired pre-shaping case. The three first synergies explain more than 65%
331 of the total variance in all the considered conditions. In the considered experiments, during contact with
332 the environment, the amount of variability accounted by higher order synergies increases. This could be
333 explained by observing that the interaction can shape the subject hand beyond its nominal kinematics. This
334 behavior is also in agreement with the findings in (Santello et al., 2002), where the synergistic analysis of
335 (Santello et al., 1998) was performed on grasped real objects instead of imagined ones.

336 Despite our inference analysis (Sec. 3.4) is limited to the first synergy, a series of characteristics of our
337 dataset can be pointed out, which are in accordance with existing neuroscientific findings. Future works
338 will focus on different experimental procedures and tasks to further investigations. In our dataset, the first
339 two synergies in the impaired and unimpaired conditions are very similar, as shown in Fig. 8 and Fig.
340 9. This suggests that the presence of tactile impairment, while modifying the strategies themselves, does
341 not substantially modify the most basic kinematic ingredients commonly used to generate hand postures.
342 Subjects are aware of the presence of the tactile impairment, so it is reasonable to expect that they might
343 have changed their planning in accordance to that. Indeed, the drop of such similarity after the third synergy
344 suggests that cutaneous impairment affects posture refinement, which can be likely ascribed to higher order
345 synergies (as described in (Santello et al., 1998)). However the amount of data collected does not allow a
346 sound statistical characterization of this behavior. To assess whether higher order synergies are primarily
347 noise or they actually contribute to hand postures, we will resort to the usage of discriminant analysis and
348 information theory, as in Santello et al. (1998), as future works.

349 Analogously, Fig. 10 shows a high similarity in the first Principal Components during contact and
350 pre-shaping, while differences can be observed for higher order synergies. Uncontrolled Manifold theory
351 (Scholz and Schöner, 1999; Latash et al., 2007) suggests that the central nervous system selects in the
352 space of joint angles a subset of variables of interest, which are regulated, purposefully leaving free the
353 remaining variables. The persistence of main postural synergies of pre-shaping during the contact with
354 the environment can be interpreted in the light of this theory by considering the first set of ECE synergies
355 as the variables of interest for the considered task, which remain constant when an external disturbance
356 occurs. The sub-space individuated by the higher order synergies is instead left free to adapt to the external
357 environment. Moreover such behaviour could also be due to peripheral constraints embedded in the
358 musculoskeletal system, as discussed e.g. in Santello et al. (2013).

359 Data shown in Fig. 9 and Table 1 demonstrate that a strong resemblance exists between the first synergy,
360 resulting from the analysis of ECE strategies, and the first synergy of grasp as found in (Santello et al.,
361 1998). This could suggest the presence of underlying synergies, which are integrated with task specific
362 ones. This was proposed e.g. in (Gorniak et al., 2007), and it is in agreement with experimental results

363 presented in (Thakur et al., 2008), where task independent synergies are estimated by a set of unconstrained
364 tasks (see CI estimates in section 3.4).

365 **4.2 Implications for robotics**

366 As it can be widely observed in literature, neuroscientific results of synergistic behavior of human
367 hands have been successfully translated and applied to robotics to inform the design, control and sensing
368 of artificial systems, with special focus on grasping, see Bicchi et al. (2011); Bianchi and Moscatelli
369 (2016). One of the first notable application of synergies to robotics was in (Brown and Asada, 2007),
370 where authors propose to use grasp synergies to derive actuation patterns for an underactuated robotic
371 hand. In (Gabicchini et al., 2011), the use of hand synergies for the choice of grasping forces is discussed.
372 In (Ciocarlie et al., 2007) and later in (Amor et al., 2012; Villani et al., 2012; Malhotra et al., 2012), a
373 synergy based low-dimensional synergistic space is considered to obtain effective pre-grasp shapes for
374 fully actuated robotic hands.

375 Recently, synergy-inspired actuation has been combined with the introduction of compliance in the
376 structure (Catalano et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2014; Della Santina et al., 2015; Chen and Xiong, 2016)
377 (according to the soft synergy framework (Bicchi et al., 2011)). The availability of robotic hands embedding
378 elasticity in their mechanics has also led to a shift in their control philosophy, accounted e.g. in (Bonilla
379 et al., 2014; Eppner and Brock, 2015). In the classical planning, suitable points are selected on the object
380 to be grasped or manipulated, generating a nominal grasp of good quality. Trajectories are then executed,
381 to correctly position the fingertips while avoiding contacts with the environment. On the contrary, soft
382 manipulation has changed this scheme. The hand-environment contacts are no more avoided but exploited
383 to successfully shape the hand around the object. Under this regard, the study of environmental exploitation
384 in humans could inform the design, planning, and control of robotic hands to take full advantage from the
385 external environment.

386 The most direct implication of the presented results could leverage upon the observation that the first
387 synergy of grasping is very similar to the first synergy for Environmental Constraint Exploitation (ECE).
388 Thus the implementation of the first synergy of grasp as degree of actuation can target the twofold goal of
389 realizing under-actuated robotic hands that can effectively grasp objects and, at the same time, are able to
390 exploit Environmental Constraints. To increase hand functionalities beyond the first degree of actuation,
391 we could implement additional ECE synergies, possibly in combination with the grasp synergies. For
392 some examples of the implementation of synergies for the design of under-actuated robotic hands, we
393 refer the interested reader to Grioli et al. (2012); Della Santina et al. (2015); Piazza et al. (2016).

394 Looking at the differences between the impaired and unimpaired conditions, the key kinematic ingredients
395 seem to remain unaltered at least for the gross movements. However, the time for task accomplishment
396 and the force exchanged with the environment is higher for the impaired case. This result could indicate
397 possible sensing strategies for soft robotic hands, i.e. to detect contact with the environment e.g. through
398 IMU sensors, which can lead to the development of planning and control laws aiming at minimizing force
399 execution on external objects.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

400 CDS, MB, MS, and AB designed the study. CDS, MB, GA, SC, VA, SF, and EB performed the experiments
401 and data analysis. CDS, MB, SC, SF, EB, and MGC designed and developed the experimental setup. All
402 authors contributed to writing the manuscript.

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ABBREVIATIONS

406 DOF, degree of freedom; EC, Environmental Constraint; ECE, Environmental Constraint Exploitation; PC,
407 Principal Component; RMSE, Root Mean Square Error; CI, confidence interval.

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APPENDIX A: FINGER KINEMATICS

The forward kinematics of a serial chain with n degrees of freedom is described by post-multiplying different rotation-translation matrices with the following form

$$T_{i-1,i} = \begin{pmatrix} R_{i-1,i} & h_{i-1,i} \\ 0_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

where $R_{i-1,i}$ is the rotation matrix between frame $i - 1$ and frame i and $h_{i-1,i}$ is the translation vector between frame $i - 1$ and frame i . Then the whole forward kinematics is calculated as

$$T_{0,n} = T_{0,1}T_{1,2} \dots T_{n-1,n}.$$

For the long finger (its kinematics is introduced in section 2.4.1.1 and parametrized with Denavit-Hartenberg in figure 4h) we have

$$T_{01} = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 & 0 & -S_1 & 0 \\ S_1 & 0 & C_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad T_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} C_2 & -S_2 & 0 & a_2C_2 \\ S_2 & C_2 & 0 & a_2S_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$T_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} C_3 & -S_3 & 0 & a_3C_3 \\ S_3 & C_3 & 0 & a_3S_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad T_{34} = \begin{pmatrix} C_4 & -S_4 & 0 & a_4C_4 \\ S_4 & C_4 & 0 & a_4S_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

where C_i stands for $\cos(q_i)$, S_i stands for $\sin(q_i)$, a_i is the length of the phalanx $i - 1$ and q_i is the i^{th} joint rotation. Then, the forward kinematics is obtained as

$$T_{04} = T_{01}T_{12}T_{23}T_{34} = \begin{pmatrix} R_{0,4} & h_{0,4} \\ 0_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The extended expression of T_{04} is neglected for simplicity and can be easily calculated by the reader. The final position $(x_{LF} \ y_{LF} \ z_{LF})^T$ of the external phalanges can be extracted from T_{04} by selecting $h_{0,4}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{LF} \\ y_{LF} \\ z_{LF} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_1(a_2C_2 + a_3C_{23} + a_4C_{234}) \\ S_1(a_2C_2 + a_3C_{23} + a_4C_{234}) \\ -a_2S_2 - a_3S_{23} - a_4S_{234} \end{pmatrix},$$

where C_{23} stands for $\cos(q_2 + q_3)$, C_{234} stands for $\cos(q_2 + q_3 + q_4)$, S_{23} stands for $\sin(q_2 + q_3)$, S_{234} stands for $\sin(q_2 + q_3 + q_4)$. The same procedure can lead to the description of the thumb forward kinematics. We have

$$T_{01} = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 & 0 & -S_1 & 0 \\ S_1 & 0 & C_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad T_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} C_2 & 0 & -S_2 & a_2C_2 \\ S_2 & 0 & C_2 & a_2S_2 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$T_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} C_3 & -S_3 & 0 & a_3C_3 \\ S_3 & C_3 & 0 & a_3S_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad T_{34} = \begin{pmatrix} C_4 & -S_4 & 0 & a_4C_4 \\ S_4 & C_4 & 0 & a_4S_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

544 and then

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_T \\ y_T \\ z_T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_4S_4(C_3S_1 - C_1C_2S_3) + a_2C_1C_2 + a_3S_1S_3 + a_4C_4(S_1S_3 + C_1C_2C_3) + a_3C_1C_2C_3 \\ a_2C_2S_1 - a_4S_4(C_1C_3 + C_2S_1S_3) - a_3C_1S_3 - a_4C_4(C_1S_3 - C_2C_3S_1) + a_3C_2C_3S_1 \\ a_4S_2S_3S_4 - a_3C_3S_2 - a_4C_3C_4S_2 - a_2S_2 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{2}$$

545 It is worth to be noticed that, while linear w.r.t. the parameters a_2, a_3, a_4 , Eq. 2 defines a strongly nonlinear
546 relationship between joint angles q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4 and LED position.

Table 1. Numerical values of the first synergy of Grasp Santello et al. (1998) and of Environmental Constraint Exploitation, with and without impairment, before and after contact. We indicate with 'x' the DoFs that were not considered in Santello et al. (1998).

DoFs	Grasp	Unimpaired Pre-Shape	Impaired Pre-Shape	Unimpaired Contact	Impaired Contact
TA	-0.43	-0.14	-0.15	-0.12	-0.15
TR	0.29	0.31	0.35	0.30	0.34
TM	0.14	0.14	0.17	0.17	0.16
TI	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.09
IA	-0.13	-0.08	-0.12	-0.08	-0.11
IM	0.33	0.39	0.35	0.40	0.34
IP	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.20
ID	x	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.05
MA	x	-0.03	-0.08	-0.02	-0.06
MM	0.33	0.38	0.33	0.38	0.32
MP	0.16	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.30
MD	x	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.08
RA	0.06	0.00	-0.02	0.02	-0.02
RM	0.40	0.44	0.37	0.43	0.32
RP	0.20	0.22	0.27	0.22	0.35
RD	x	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.11
LA	0.14	0.05	0.1	0.08	0.09
LM	0.37	0.43	0.42	0.41	0.37
LP	0.27	0.12	0.21	0.17	0.24
LD	x	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.08